

FUNCTIONAL INTERACTIONS BETWEEN LNCRNAS, MIRNAS, AND MRNAS IN CANCER RESISTANCE TO CHEMOTHERAPY

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Abstract

Environmental and genetic factors are two of the variables that might affect cancer, making it a complex disease. Due to its rising incidence, cancer is tragically now the second leading cause of death globally, after heart disease. Chemotherapy's main goal is to prevent the cancer cells from proliferating. The medications can kill cancer cells faster and more efficiently than other surrounding cells because they multiply and spread dramatically more quickly than healthy cells and have extremely significant levels of endogenous stress. Non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs) are those that do not encode proteins. Numerous ncRNAs, such as long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), have been recognized as playing crucial parts in the initiation and spread of human malignancies. Drug resistance, the onset of BC, and the progression of metastases are all significantly influenced by long noncoding RNAs. Several examples of lncRNA and miRNA that show resistance to chemotherapy in different cancer types. This review discussed different types of ncRNAs, their mechanism of resistance to chemotherapy, lncRNAs and miRNAs that show resistance to chemotherapy, and the future strategies to overcome the resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is an unpredictable disease that is caused by variables including environmental influences and genetics. After cardiovascular disease, cancer is now the second major cause of death globally. In 2018, approximately 9.6 million cancer-related fatalities and 18.1 million new cases were reported by the American Cancer Society. This suggests that treatment plans require more focus (Bray et al.,

2018; You & Henneberg, 2018). As far as incidence and mortality is concerned, liver carcinoma (8.2%), colorectal carcinoma (CRC) (10.2%), stomach cancer (8.2%), breast cancer (11.6%), prostate cancer (7.1%), are the notable cancer that are diagnosed and the leading cause of cancer-related death (18.4% of all cancer deaths). A common cancer found in both males and females is lung cancer (Bray et al.,

2018). Although the immune responses should be capable of efficiently combating tumors by eliminating the altered cells, several factors, such as the biological characteristics of the tumor microenvironment (TME), cause local antitumor immune responses to be suppressed. In order to initiate, promote, and spread their tumor, tumor cells develop unique environments around themselves (Hui & Chen, 2015; Maimela, Liu, & Zhang, 2019). The TME may also contain other cell types besides tumor cells, such as stromal cells, fibroblasts, and leukocytes. Tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes, myeloid-derived suppressor cells, tumor-associated fibroblasts, tumor-associated macrophages, tumor-associated neutrophils, cancer stem cells, and mesenchymal stem cells are the most common cells in the TME (Galdiero, Varricchi, Loffredo, Mantovani, & Marone, 2018; Wels, Kaplan, Rafii, & Lyden, 2008). To cure cancer, a variety of treatments have been used, including immunotherapy, surgery, hormone therapy, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and different kinds of RNA molecular injections. One of the most effective options is chemotherapy among them, particularly for malignancies that have spread (Baskar, Lee, Yeoh, & Yeoh, 2012).

Overview of chemotherapy

Chemotherapy mainly prevents the proliferation and spreading of cancer cells. As a Part of their accelerated growth and division, cancer cells also exhibit dramatically elevated levels of endogenous stress. As a result, they can be targeted by the drugs faster and more effectively than other cells in the surrounding. Hedgehog pathway blockers, histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors, angiogenesis inhibitors, tyrosine kinase inhibitors, polyadenosine diphosphate-ribose polymerase inhibitors, poly (adenosine diphosphate-ribose) polymerase (PARP) inhibitors, hedgehog pathway blockers, mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) inhibitors, proteasome inhibitors, hedgehog pathway inhibitors, and hedgehog pathway blockers are among the capable inhibitor therapies that have been applied to treat cancers. (Dewanjee et al., 2021; Sawyers, 2004). Chemotherapy comes in a variety of forms that can impact the target cells differently. (Mattheolabakis, Rigas, & Constantinides, 2012). Major chaperone

repressors, protease inhibitors, and autophagy suppressors are a few examples of treatments that can directly change the composition of proteins in cells, turning them non-functional and disrupting critical functional circuits. (Jinghong Chen et al., 2020; Hasima & Ozpolat, 2014; Leu, Pimkina, Pandey, Murphy, & George, 2011; Sannino et al., 2018; Selimovic et al., 2013). The significant role of immunotherapy, which is the basis for the possibility of changing our immune system to help us combat cancer-like situations and ward off the illness, has been highlighted by the 2018 Nobel Award for research on immunological checkpoint therapy. (Kroemer & Zitvogel, 2021; Mattheolabakis et al., 2012). The key variables of the chemo preventive drugs or mixture of medications employed are the kind and stage of cancer. The primary objectives of these drugs are to eliminate the oncogenic cells and reduce the stress that is caused by the growth of the tumor. Duration and dosage of the medication are two important considerations. The medications are given at very high dosages, which may harm other healthy cells and cause several harmful consequences, as has been observed. (Torino et al., 2013). However, prolonged usage of these drugs can affect the physical and mental health of patients that making it tough to continue the treatment. Most cancer experts administer these medications with possible intervals, which also promotes the healing of non-converted cells (Mahner et al., 2013).

LncRNA in mediating resistance

RNA products that do not encode proteins are known as non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs) (Poller et al., 2018; Sakamoto et al., 2017). Non-coding RNAs are categorized based on their size into long and tiny ncRNAs (<200 nucleotides, nt) (L-L. Chen & Kim, 2024). Molecules of non-coding RNA are larger than 200 nts (contain less than 100 amino acids for coding) and do not have a clearly defined open reading frame are known as LncRNAs (R. Li, Zhu, & Luo, 2016). LncRNA genes can be categorized into five classes according to where they are located in reference to the next protein-coding gene: (i) sense lncRNAs, which are deposited on the coding strand of a protein-coding gene beneath its exons; (ii) antisense lncRNAs, which emerge on the noncoding strand of a protein-coding gene and are

superimposed on its exons; (iii) bidirectional lncRNAs, that are transcribed from the jump of another transcript; (iv) intronic long noncoding RNAs, that are completely contained within the intron of another transcript; and (v) long intergenic noncoding RNAs that divide a pair protein-coding genes (Tony Gutschner & Diederichs, 2012). Generally stated, lncRNAs exhibit differential expression across tissues, illnesses, and even at particular stages of illness, highlighting their potential as attractive targets for treatment of the condition (G. Li, Deng, Huang, & Sun, 2021). While the functions of short non-coding RNAs, like small interfering RNAs (siRNAs), microRNAs (miRNAs), and PIWI-interacting RNAs (piRNAs) have all been widely and critically examined elsewhere, and it is known that a range of lncRNAs are important for the proliferation of cancers in humans (Martens-Uzunova et al., 2014; Schmitz, Grote, & Herrmann, 2016; H. Zhang et al., 2013)., microRNAs—a household of endogenous, short non-coding RNAs that are around 22 nucleotides long—post transcriptionally control gene expression (Catalanotto, Cogoni, & Zardo, 2016). More than 50% of protein-coding genes are regulated by microRNAs, and each miRNA is expected to suppress multiple mRNA substrates (Krol, Loedige, & Filipowicz, 2010). There are presently 2,578 mature human microRNA sequences known to exist (miRbase version 20, June 2013). Numerous significant processes in biology, including organ development, the biotransformation of endogenous substances, proliferation and cell differentiation, foreign substances, and apoptosis, are increasingly being linked to these RNA molecules (Kahraman, 2022). Numerous liver illnesses (nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), viral hepatitis, polycystic liver disease, and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) have been linked to microRNAs (X.-M. Chen, 2009).

Role of lncRNA in drug efflux

Increased efflux of drugs from overexpression of the human ATP-binding cassette (ABC) makes it a challenge to retain the therapeutic intracellular concentration of the drug and ultimately causes the failure of antineoplastic therapy. There are 49 recognized transporters in the ATP-binding cassette protein that control the distribution, excretion, and

absorption of pharmaceutical substances (Breier, Gibalova, Seres, Barancik, & Sulova, 2013). Certain ABC proteins, including adenosine triphosphate-binding cassette, superfamily G, multidrug resistance-associated protein (MRP), P-glycoprotein (P-gp), and member 2 (ABCG2), are commonly overexpressed in different forms of cancer, including breast and ovarian cancer (H. Cui, J. Zhang, Chen, & J. Liu, 2015; Iangcharoen et al., 2011). P-gp levels are elevated in tumor cells may be caused by several kinases, such as MEK1, MEK2, H-Ras, Raf-1, and the overexpression of these proteins may also result from cellular environmental stressors. For instance, overexpression of the linc-VLDLR and lncRNAs H19 increased the expression of MDR1/P-gp and ABCG2 in hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC); increased expression of the lncRNAs PVT1 and MRL increased the ATP-binding cassette, expression of MDR1, subfamily B, member 1 (ABCB1) in gastric cancer (GC); and elevated levels of the lncRNA AK022798 caused the upregulation of P-gp and MRP1 in drug-resistant cells (J. Kong, Qiu, Li, Zhang, & Wang, 2019; Majidinia & Yousefi, 2016). Due to particular lncRNAs, breast cancer cells may overexpress ABC efflux transporters, which might result in MDR (Z. Chen et al., 2016). ABC efflux transporter protein MRPI is sometimes overexpressed by MCF-7 cells because lncRNA sponging of miR-199a controls the production of ABC efflux transporters in MCF-7 BCE cells. One example is the competitive endogenous RNA (ceRNA) lncRNA linc00518 that sponges miR-199a. Linc00518 knockdown using si-linc00518 increases MDR MCF-7 BCE cells' sensitivity to some cytotoxic medications, including paclitaxel (PTX), vincristine (VCR), and adriamycin (ADR) (Chang, Hu, Zhou, & Zhang, 2018). It has been shown that the lncRNA EPB41L4A-AS2 declines in docetaxel (DOC)-resistant MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 BCE cells, and that under expression of EPB41L4A-AS2 in BC cells is correlated with overexpression of ABCB1 and the development of DOC resistance. (Haung et al., 2018). Since most chemotherapeutic medications prevent cancer cells from growing by causing apoptosis, treatment resistance is also affected when apoptosis is disrupted (Neophytou, Trougakos, Erin, & Papageorgis, 2021). The survival factors that are increased and stop programmed cell death include

nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), Bcl-2 family proteins. According to Zhang et al., PVT1 overexpression in cisplatin-resistant cancer cells leads to less cell death following cisplatin therapy (X.-w. Zhang, Bu, Liu, Zhang, & Li, 2015). In cisplatin-resistant lung cancer cells, the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway regulated Bcl-XL and p53 expression to reduce lncRNA MEG3 expression and increase the cells' receptivity to cisplatin treatment (J. Liu et al., 2015). Both proapoptotic proteins like BAK, BAX, BAD, and BIK and antiapoptotic proteins like Bcl-2 and Bcl-XL are members of the Bcl-2 protein family and are crucial elements in the mitochondrial apoptotic process (Youle & Strasser, 2008). By interfering with the production of the proapoptotic proteins FAS, BAX, and BAK, the lncRNA H19 helps induce cisplatin lung cancer resistance (Q. Wang et al., 2016). However, the lncRNA ENST00000457645 promotes BAX-associated cell death, which dramatically reduces the cisplatin resistance of CD70 cells (Yan, Xia, & Feng, 2017). According to general theories, lncRNAs might increase radiosensitivity by influencing the death of cancer cells and proliferation. They do so primarily via controlling key signal transduction pathways, like the Wnt/ β -catenin and PI3K/AKT pathways, and by functioning as miRNA sponges (Zhu et al., 2019). Many cancer-treating chemotherapeutic medications work by triggering apoptosis pathways, particularly

those mediated by caspases, either intrinsically or extrinsically. The two main mechanisms that regulate the apoptosis pathways in the pathophysiology progression of cancer are the upregulation of anti-apoptotic proteins and downregulation of pro-apoptotic proteins (Q. Cui et al., 2018; Kopecka et al., 2020; Levin, Stark, Ofran, & Assaraf, 2021; Pfeffer & Singh, 2018; Shahar & Larisch, 2020; Šimoničová et al., 2022). LncRNAs connected to the pathway of apoptosis have been connected to BC of MDR in several studies. LncRNAs shield cancer cells from apoptosis brought on by DNA damage or oxidative stress caused by specific cytotoxic medications. LncRNA SNHG14 reduced cell death induced by trastuzumab and boosted BC proliferation and opposition to trastuzumab via activating the Nrf2 signaling pathway (H. Dong et al., 2018). A study using preclinical and clinical models revealed that BC cells and tumors have a significant level of upregulation of the lncRNA MALAT1. Moreover, BC patients with MALAT1 overexpression profiles had a worse prognosis. MALAT1 expression was significantly higher in tumor cell culture assays involving resistance to drugs MCF-7/ADR and MCF-7/Tax BC cells that are resistant to adriamycin (ADR) and tamoxifen (Tax), respectively. For the MALAT1 knockdown trials, sensitivity to Tax and ADR was significantly elevated (J. Yu, Jin, & Zhang, 2020).

Figure 1: Role of lncRNA in Drug Resistance.

When it comes to treating breast cancer, DOX is the most often utilized chemotherapy drug. Tumor grade and anatomic stage are frequently considered components in the assessment of risk and chemosensitivity. Higher-risk malignancies (i.e., those with a higher grade or in later stages) typically improve more from chemotherapy (Waks & Winer, 2019). Resistance of the drug, the onset of BC, & the metastasis progression is all significantly influenced by lncRNAs. The progression of BC is greatly aided by aberrant expression of the HOX transcript analogous intergenic RNA (HOTAIR) lncRNA, which is a predictor of BC metastasis (Cantile et al., 2020). The chondroitin sulfotransferase CHST15 (carbohydrate N-acetyl galactosamine 4-sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 15; GalNAc4S-6ST), an enzyme that catalyzes the sulfation of N-acetyl galactosamine 4-sulfate at position 6 to form glycosaminoglycans composed of N-acetyl galactosamine 4,6-bisulfate and disaccharide units of glucuronic acid (GlcA), is preferentially elevated by HOTAIR (L. C. Liu et al., 2019). The chondroitin sulfotransferase CHST15 is targeted by HOX transcript antisense intergenic RNA

(HOTAIR) in cell lines of breast cancer, and this enzyme is required for HOTAIR-mediated invasiveness (L. C. Liu et al., 2019).

Long non-coding RNA MALAT1, by binding to the transcriptional factor STAT3, can control the production of the efflux transporters MDR1 and MRP1. MALAT1 expression is upregulated in A549 lung cancer cells resistant to cisplatin. Overexpression of MALAT1 increases MRP1 and MDR1 expression, which reduces cisplatin sensitivity in vivo and in vitro (C. Y. Li & Cui, 2018). Signal transmitter and activator of transcription protein 3 (STAT3) is a crucial transcription factor that heavily influences the transcriptional control of MDR1 and MRPs gene expressions (Xi et al., 2015). The notable reason for treatment failure in patients affected by cancer, multiple drug resistance (MDR), has a complicated molecular background. MDR-related proteins are essential for MDR, including MDR1 (also called ABCB1, P-gp) and multidrug resistance proteins (MRPs) (J. Wang et al., 2011).

miRNA role in drug efflux's

The widely recognized tumor opposing pathways are mediated by ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter

proteins. ABCB1 and ABCC1 may be targeted by miRNA-223 and miRNA-133a, respectively, making HCC cells more susceptible to DOX (Lee, 2009; J. Ma et al., 2015; T. Yang et al., 2013) An anticancer medication with a broad spectrum of action, CDDP creates DNA adducts and crosslinks, which eventually result in replication breaks double-strand. Research has indicated that variations in the miRNA-96 expression (Yemin Wang, Huang, Calses, Kemp, & Taniguchi, 2012), miRNA-340 (Shi et al., 2015), miRNA-130a (Xu, Shen, et al., 2012), miRNA-182 (Qin, Luo, Qian, & Chen, 2014), and miRNA-199a-5p (Xu, Zhang, et al., 2012) May either enhance or decrease HCC's susceptibility to CDDP. One of the first-line chemotherapeutic treatments for lung cancer is CDDP. Research demonstrated that let-7c (Zhan, Qu, Wang, & Zhou, 2013) Targeting distinct genes, miRNA-31 (Z. Dong, Zhong, Yang, Wang, & Gong, 2014), miRNA-182 (Ning et al., 2014), miRNA-224 (H. Wang, Zhu, Yang, Wang, & Wang, 2014), miRNA-138 (Q. Wang et al., 2011), miRNA-205 (L. Lei, Huang, & Gong, 2013), miRNA-15b (Zhao, Zhang, Yao, & Tao, 2015), miRNA-106a (Y. Ma, Li, Cheng, Wei, & Li, 2015), , miRNA-513a-3p (X. Zhang et al., 2012), miRNA-27a (J. Li, Wang, Song, Fu, & Yu, 2014), and miRNA-92b (Y. Li et al., 2013) and miRNA-34a (G. Yu, Zhong, Chen, Huang, & Wu, 2014) May control CDDP tolerance in NSCLC. ABCC2, an ATP-dependent transport protein, reduces the intracellular concentration of drugs while increasing their efflux. According to studies, miRNAs like let-7 (Boyerinas et al., 2012), , miRNA-9 (Sun et al., 2013), miRNA-130b (C. Yang et al., 2012), miRNA-370 (X.-P. Chen, Chen, Lan, & Shen, 2014), miRNA-489 (H. Wu et

al., 2014), and miRNA-449a (Y. Zhou, Chen, Qin, Zhang, & Li, 2014) and miRNA-199b-5p (M. X. Liu et al., 2013) It could decrease the CDDP resistance in ovarian cancer cells.

Different types of cancer were treated with different types of drugs. When a drug is influxes into the cells, its main target is to damage DNA and lead to apoptosis, but miRNA dysregulation leads to resistance inside the cell. miRNA leads to drug metabolism to overcome the effect of the drug. Genes associated with pharmacokinetics, DNA damage repair, anticancer drug targets, and essential genes in drug action signaling pathways are among the important target genes connected. Together, they form a regulatory network for sensitivity to chemotherapy. (Si, Shen, Zheng, & Fan, 2019) The primary target of fluoropyrimidine medications used to treat colorectal cancer is thymine synthase (TS), which is specifically targeted by miR-215 and miR-192. By suppressing miR-192, miR-215, and TS expression, dramatically raises colon cancer cells' susceptibility to 5FU (Giovannetti, Erozeenci, Smit, Danesi, & Peters, 2012). Overexpression of multidrug resistance-associated protein 1 MRP1, an efflux transporter) It is often the cause of chemotherapy resistance in breast cancer. By inhibiting MRP1 expression, miR-145 can make breast cancer cells more vulnerable to doxorubicin (Gao et al., 2016). When drugs lead to DNA damage inside the cell, special miRNAs miR-149 and miR-488 regulate important genes that are involved in DNA repairing, including excision repair cross-complementation group 1 (ERCC1) and XPC (H. Yang et al., 2023).

Key ncRNA resistance to chemotherapy

Table 1: Examples of LncRNA that show resistance to chemotherapy

s.no	MiRNA type	Cancer type	Chemotherapy resistance	Result	References
1	miR-21	Gastric ulcer	Cisplatin	miR-21 expression was elevated in the cisplatin-resistant SGC7901/DDP cells compared to the parental SGC7901 line. Its overexpression reduced cisplatin-induced apoptosis and growth	(S.-m. Yang et al., 2013)

				inhibition, whereas silencing miR-21 enhanced these effects. miR-21 promoted cisplatin resistance by suppressing PTEN and activating the Akt pathway, while the PI3K inhibitor LY294002 reversed this resistance by blocking Akt activation.	
2	miR-155	Triple negative breast cancer	Decitabine	miR-155 was upregulated in breast cancer stem cells (CD24–CD44+). Its overexpression in BT-549 and MDA-MB-231 cells enhanced tumor colony formation, DCA resistance, and the CD24–CD44+ stem cell population, while miR-155 knockdown reduced stemness and DCA resistance. Tetraspanin-5 (TSPAN5) was identified as the direct target suppressed by miR-155, promoting stemness and drug resistance.	(L. W. Yang et al., 2020)
3	miR-181b	Pancreatic cancer	Gemcitabine	Compared to MiaPaCa2 cells, BxPC3, Panc1, and PSN1 pancreatic cancer cells showed higher miR-181b expression. Transfection with pre-miR-181b increased gemcitabine resistance in MiaPaCa2 cells, while anti-miR-181b reduced resistance and induced apoptosis in the other cell lines. miR-181b promoted gemcitabine resistance by inhibiting CYLD and activating NF-κB signaling.	(Takiuchi et al., 2013)
4	miR-125b	Ovarian cancer	Cisplatin	miR-125b overexpression increased cisplatin resistance in OV2008 and C13* cells by suppressing cisplatin-induced cytotoxicity and apoptosis. It directly targeted and inhibited Bak1, whose suppression further enhanced resistance and reduced apoptosis. These findings indicate that elevated miR-125b promotes chemoresistance in C13* cells by downregulating Bak1 expression.	(Fanfei Kong et al., 2011)
5	miR-21-5p	Gastric cancer	Doxorubicin	Both DOX-resistant GC cells and patient tissue samples had increased expression of miR-21-	(Jun Chen et al., 2018)

				5p. When miR-21-5p levels were reduced, GC cells were more vulnerable to DOX-based chemotherapy because it directly raised TIMP3 and PTEN. This indicates that a good therapeutic strategy for GC may involve the antagonism of DOX and miR-21-5p.	
6	miR-17-5p	Colorectal cancer	MDR	CRC patients with advanced stages and distant metastases showed significantly elevated miR-17-5p expression. Kaplan-Meier analysis indicated that high miR-17-5p levels were linked to poorer survival, particularly in chemotherapy-treated patients. Overexpression of miR-17-5p increased COLO205 cell invasiveness by targeting PTEN, contributing to treatment resistance through context-specific interactions.	(L. Fang et al., 2014)
7	miR-19a/b	Gastric cancer	MDR	MDR gastric cancer tissues exhibited elevated miR-19a/b levels. Upregulation of miR-19a/b reduced the sensitivity of GC cells to anticancer drugs by regulating Bcl-2 and Bax, thereby suppressing drug-induced apoptosis. It also enhanced ADR efflux by increasing mdr1 and P-gp expression. PTEN, an inhibitor of AKT phosphorylation, was identified as the direct target of miR-19a/b, indicating that miR-19a/b promotes multidrug resistance in GC cells through PTEN suppression.	(F. Wang et al., 2013)
8	miR-203	Colorectal cancer	Oxaliplatin	Exogenous expression of miR-203 induced oxaliplatin resistance in chemo-naïve colorectal cancer cells, while miR-203 knockdown restored drug sensitivity. miR-203 directly targeted ATM in CRC cells, and mutations in the miR-203 binding site within the ATM 3'UTR abolished this regulation. Similarly,	(Yunfei Zhou et al., 2014)

				stable ATM knockdown also conferred oxaliplatin resistance, confirming ATM as a key mediator of miR-203-induced chemoresistance.	
9	miR-20	Gastric cancer	Cisplatin	There was a considerable increase in miR-20a levels in both tissue and GC plasma. It was also discovered to be elevated in GC plasma and tissues from patients with the SGC7901/cisplatin (DDP...) gastric cancer cell line, which is resistant to cisplatin. Concurrently with livin, miR-20a, p65, and survivin were upregulated, and NFKBIB (also known as IκBβ) was downregulated. Transfection of SGC7901/DDP cells with a miR-20a inhibitor may increase the quantity of NFKBIB, decrease the expression of livin, p65, and survivin, and increase the proportion of apoptotic cells. The results suggested that miR-20a may influence GC chemoresistance by targeting NFKBIB and encouraging the activation of the NFκB pathway and its downstream substrates, survivin and livin.	(Yiping Du et al., 2016)
10	miR-146a-5p	Breast cancer	Trastuzumab	By upregulating migration and angiogenesis and downregulating CDKN1A expression, miR-146a-5p overexpression promoted cell cycle advancement. Exosomes from cells resistant to trastuzumab expressed more miR-146a-5p than exosomes from the parent cells. Moreover, co-cultivating resistant cells with their exosomes increased the motility of trastuzumab-sensitive cells while decreasing sensitivity and	(Cabello et al., 2023)

				promoting angiogenesis in cells of HUVEC-2.	
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Overcoming resistance: Novel therapeutic approaches

Strategies for miRNA to treat human cancers

A new cancer treatment strategy called miRNA-based gene therapy is gaining traction since miRNAs play a part in metastasis, tumor invasion, and proliferation. MiRNA activity is lowered when oncomiR is elevated, and it is restored when tumor suppressor miRNA is suppressed. The goal of these two treatment modalities is to get tumor cells to produce miRNA normally again.

Inhibition therapy of miRNA

To restore normal expression and function of tumor suppressor genes, miRNA inhibition therapy can be used by blocking oncomiRs, which are suggestively upregulated in tumor cells, using antisense anti-miR oligonucleotides (AMO), miRNA antagomirs, miRNA sponges, and locked nucleic acid (Shah, Ferrajoli, Sood, Lopez-Berestein, & Calin, 2016). Fundamentally corresponding to a single-stranded oligonucleotide, miRNA inhibitors can isolate the endogenous miRNA in an unidentifiable structure, which in turn renders the mature miRNAs inactive and extracts them from the RISC. The purpose of single-stranded, chemically modified AMOs, or antisense oligonucleotides, is to complement a miRNA of interest. They are 17–22 nucleotides long (Garzon, Marcucci, & Croce, 2010). A modified AMO is exemplified by LNA, an antisense oligonucleotide designed to bind to appropriate mature miRNA, stopping it from interacting with its specific messenger RNA targets, for normal translation (Vester & Wengel, 2004). In an in vivo investigation, Griveau et al. describe that in glioblastomas, overexpressed miR-21 may be suppressed by LNA-modified antisense

oligonucleotides, which would improve intracellular caspase and significantly reduce cell survival (Griveau et al., 2013). Chemically modified 23-nucleotide RNA molecules of single-strand known as antagomirs work in tandem with the specific miRNAs to improve RNA stability and prevent degradation (Czech, 2006; Krützfeldt et al., 2005). Ma et al. claimed that antagomir-induced decrease of miR-10b stopped metastasis in a mouse model of breast cancer. They also observed that HOXD10, a functionally necessary miR-10b receiver, had its levels significantly raised and miR-10b levels drastically decreased when antagomirs were used to silence this miRNA (L. Ma et al., 2010). OncomiRs have been suppressed with miRNA sponges in addition to LNA treatment. MiRNA wedges contain several synthetic miRNA binding sites, which compete with native microRNA target genes for miRNA binding (Ebert & Sharp, 2010). miR-9 was overexpressed in breast cancer, preventing the tumor regulator gene CDH1 from being expressed. Four miR-9 binding sites on miRNA sponges allowed them to effectively suppress miR-9's function and restore CDH1's endogenous expression, which in turn prevented metastases (Hildebrandt et al., 2010). An artificial miRNA sponge with a revolutionary design was recently created. Inspired by endogenous miRNA sponges, which are naturally occurring circular RNA (circRNA), a practical artificial circRNA slug was created by a straightforward ligation enzymatic process. The therapeutic potential of this manufactured circRNA molecule was demonstrated by its effective binding and inhibition of mature RNA, which was intended as an exogenous miRNA inhibitor (X. Liu et al., 2018).

Restoration therapy of miRNA:

Through the reestablishment of exogenous cancer suppressor miRNAs that have been inhibited in cancer cells, miRNA restoration treatment could either induce programmed cell death or halt the proliferation of oncogenic cells. To perform

microRNA restoration therapy, synthetic miRNA viral vectors or mimics that produce miRNAs can be employed. miRNA mimics can restore endogenous miRNAs to their typical function and replace missing miRNAs. The RNA duplexes can be loaded into RISC to provide downstream suppression of target messenger RNAs (Shah et al., 2016). The efficacy of miRNA restoration treatment has been shown in numerous investigations, both in vivo and in vitro. For example, cell lines for prostate cancer experienced considerable apoptosis & decreased proliferation when miRNA mimic miR-15 was added (Bonci et al., 2008). By blocking cell cycle pathways and cell proliferation, the intranasal delivery of let-7 effectively inhibited the formation of tumors in the K-ras mutant animal used in the in vivo investigation (Esquela-Kerscher et al., 2008; Trang et al., 2010). Using expression vectors of miRNA, including retroviral, adenoviral, and lentiviral vectors, to boost the expression that suppresses tumors is another tactic of miRNA restoration treatment. Kota et al. discovered that human liver tumors lost miR-26, despite the fact that it was abundantly expressed in normal cells. It has been demonstrated that ectopic production of this miRNA results in cell cycle arrest in liver carcinoma cells. Recombinant adenovirus containing miR-26 was injected intravenously, and without causing any damage, it increased tumor apoptosis and suppressed cell proliferation, hence reducing tumorigenicity. (Kota et al., 2009).

Therapeutic strategies for lncRNA

Long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) (transcripts with more than 200 nucleotides) can regulate the progression of colorectal cancer (CRC) by acting as competitive endogenous RNAs (ceRNAs), interacting with miRNAs or generating short peptides and protein-coding mRNAs (L. Wang et al., 2019). Long intergenic nonprotein-coding RNA 689 (LINC00689) behaved as a miR-31-5p absorb to prevent metastasis, proliferation, and chemoresistance in colorectal cancer by overexpressing tumor inhibitor kinase (LATS2) and suppressing the yes-associated protein (YAP)/ β -catenin signaling pathway. Additionally, re-modulating the expression of the abnormal lncRNAs can help treat colorectal cancer (CRC), as a growing

number of studies indicate that these lncRNAs contribute to medication resistance in the disease.

Antisense oligonucleotides

Antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs) can induce RNase-H-mediated RNA hydrolysis by forming a DNA-RNA structure with the targeting RNA, utilizing base pairing principles. Clinical testing has shown that ASOs can target mRNA in cancer (Bennett, Baker, Pham, Swayze, & Geary, 2017). MALAT1 was struck down by ASO, which significantly reduces metastasis and tumor growth, including lung cancer (T. Gutschner et al., 2013) and breast cancer (Arun et al., 2016). According to one study, ASO-mediated down-regulation of lncRNA-SChLAP1 decreased metastasis and tumor growth in a small percentage of patients who express the second chromosomal locus linked to prostate-1 (SChLAP1) lncRNA (Huarte, 2015).

CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing technique

While dealing with cancer, CRISPR/Cas9 has also drawn a lot of attention as a technique for targeted gene DNA alteration. According to recent studies, CRISPR/Cas9 can successfully prevent the gene expression of loci encoding lncRNA (Gilbert et al., 2014; Koch, 2017). The CRISPR/Cas9 system has been used to target the tumor cells of genomic DNA and models of animal cancer models. For example, deleting lncRNA-MALAT1 and lncRNA-NEAT1 dramatically decreased the capacity of cancer cells to proliferate. (Adriaens et al., 2016; Mendell, 2016). Cancer cells' chemosensitivity and replication stress response are regulated by lncRNA-NEAT1. Precancerous cells evolved into being more susceptible to cell death brought on by DNA damage when lncRNA-NEAT1 was knocked out, and chemotherapy medications became more destructive to cancer cells. (Adriaens et al., 2016). A well-planned proof-of-concept animal study found that giving mice a CRISPR/Cas9 system that targets GMAN significantly decreased the spread of gastritis tumor tissues and improved overall survival (Zhuo et al., 2019).

Short hairpin RNAs (Viruses)

The application of shRNAs to target lncRNAs in cancer treatment has been extensively documented. In a recent study, the lncRNA-BCAR4 elimination cell line produced by lentiviral transfection significantly decreased the in vivo development of cancer of breast cancer metastases in mice (Xing et al., 2014). Furthermore, A viral infection that transfects a stomach cancer cell line with HOTAIR shRNA significantly minimizes the cells' capacity to proliferate through peritoneal dissemination (Endo et al., 2013). Additionally, it was discovered that by blocking the production of metastatic Ki-67, adenovirus-mediated lncRNA-PNUTS knockdown could decrease the incidence of breast cancer in its primary stage and its metastases (Grelet et al., 2017).

Future directions for ncRNAs in targeted chemotherapy

The complicated roles and activities of lncRNAs are being clarified by compiling lncRNA databases, and predictive algorithms are being created to identify their relationships with cellular type, localization, and disease association (Fukunaga, Iwakiri, Ono, & Hamada, 2019; Seifuddin et al., 2020; Y. Wang et al., 2021). An interesting new mechanism that may increase our understanding of the spatiotemporal regulation of cellular processes and lead to novel therapeutic options is the ability of long noncoding RNAs to bind to proteins and produce phase-separated droplets (Luo et al., 2021). It is also convincing that lncRNAs can be clinical targets in GC since they control tumor micro-regulatory networks, and that lncRNA activation may affect several tumor-associated pathways (Tan et al., 2020). Decades have passed since it became clear that future cancer treatments depend on identifying the important chemicals and/or the TME signaling pathways. In this regard, it has been found that lncRNAs control a range of cytokines and immune cells, including the superfamily of TGF- β (Jing, Li, Han, & Shi, 2020; K. Lei et al., 2017; Sakai et al., 2019; Xiong, Yang, Chen, & Fan, 2015; Q. Zhang, Chen, Liu, & Yang, 2018), IFN family (C. J. Wang et al., 2019), IL family (Jing et al., 2020; R. Zhou, Wu, Deng, & Chen, 2019) and related signaling pathways (F. Kong et al., 2018; Y. Zhang et al., 2019). Using techniques like antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs),

small interference RNAs (siRNAs), lncRNA-targeted drugs, CRISPR-Cas9, and others, it is possible to target lncRNAs and achieve dependable therapy results. However, the application of what is known about lncRNAs to therapeutic contexts is relatively limited. First, there is a belief that the existing mechanistic analysis of lncRNAs in GC is inadequate. Recent research indicates that a considerable number of lncRNAs are implicated in biological processes in GC, including proliferation, drug resistance, cell metastasis, and apoptosis, despite a number of gaps. Investigations into the basic mechanisms of lncRNA-associated GC may provide support for the anti-GC campaign (Y. Li et al., 2021). Since these lncRNAs alter crucial signaling pathways, they can serve as innovative molecular targets for PCa prognosis and therapy, which are implicated in numerous aspects of prostate carcinogenesis. Furthermore, new approaches to targeted gene therapy have been made possible by advancements in CRISPR technology, viral delivery methods, and RNA-guided endogenous CRISPR activation (CRISPRa), including adenoviruses, adeno-associated viruses (AAVs), and lentiviruses (Y. Chen, Li, Chen, & Zhang, 2021; S. J. Liu & Lim, 2018). Targeting the expression of miR-23a, adenovirus vector-mediated lncRNA XIST overexpression was recently discovered to be a tumor suppressor that prevented PCa metastasis both in vitro and in vivo (Y. Du et al., 2017).

Future therapeutic effects of miRNAs have been demonstrated by two clinical studies. A phase 2a clinical trial was conducted in which 26 patients with genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) were treated with Miravirsin, a nucleic acid-modified DNA phosphorothioate antisense oligonucleotide that suppresses the action of mature miR-122 by wrapping it in a heteroduplex. The experiment has not yet shown any adverse side effects (Janssen et al., 2013). For patients with liver cancer or metastatic cancer who have liver issues, MRX34, a copy of the suppressor of tumors miR-34, was being evaluated in a phase 1 clinical trial. In this study, MRX34's safety and efficacy are being evaluated in both healthy volunteers and patients with metastatic or advanced hepatocellular carcinoma (Ling, Fabbri, & Calin, 2013).

Conclusion

Many therapeutic strategies have been used to treat cancer using chemotherapy, even though cancer is a complicated disease that can spread in a variety of ways. This evaluation highlights concern about the ncRNA-mediated cancer chemoresistance, such as lncRNAs, miRNAs, and mRNA chemoresistance to chemotherapy. Different types of drugs have been introduced to treat cancers, such as cisplatin, doxorubicin, oxaliplatin, Methotrexate, decitabine, and many more, but dysregulation of non-coding RNAs leads to chemoresistance and supports cancer cells by preventing them from DNA damage and cell apoptosis, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Whenever a drug is entered into the cell, dysregulated non-coding RNAs change the composition of the drug to get rid of DNA damage or cell apoptosis of the cell. In this review, we have discussed how lncRNA and miRNA show chemoresistance and support the cancer cells by showing drug efflux. Different examples of lncRNAs and miRNAs have been mentioned in this review. We have also discussed different therapeutic strategies to overcome lncRNAs resistance, such as CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing technique, Antisense oligonucleotides, and short hairpin viruses. For miRNAs therapeutic strategies include miRNA inhibition and restoration therapy to overcome the chemoresistance shown by noncoding RNAs to reduce the death rate of cancer patients worldwide.

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